

METHODS OF TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES.

Djuraeva Namuna Vakhobjan qizi

Head of the Department of Interfaculty Pedagogy and Psychology of KSPI

Abdumalikova Gulkhumor Nasirjon qizi, student of KSPI

Mukhammadalieva Rukhshonabonu Shukhratjon qizi, student of KSPI

Abstract: This material discusses the possibility of using some pedagogical technologies in mathematics lessons.

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Our new twenty-first century is the time when the development of information technologies came to the fore. Not a month goes by without some new invention being announced somewhere in the world. Now most of human life is controlled by smart gadgets. As you know, the basis of all these newfangled inventions is calculation and exact calculation, more precisely, mathematics. It is called the queen of all sciences. It must be admitted that this subject is one of the most difficult subjects to study from the subjects of a secondary general education school. Teachers of this discipline have an order of magnitude more difficult than other teachers in the learning process to arouse students' interest in their subject. Teachers in the primary grades have to be especially resourceful. In the course of numerous studies and observations, it has been found that susceptibility to the subjects studied at school can develop in children in a positive way. A child who, for example, experienced certain difficulties in spelling letters or signs, can significantly improve his performance in this direction at school. The same can be said about reading lessons - a student who in preschool found it difficult to remember the names of letters or retell various texts, at school can learn to read quickly and retell any kind of text from memory. But the same cannot be said about mathematics.[1] As noted, children who had difficulties with this subject in kindergarten exacerbated their problems in the realities of primary school. To put it simply, a child who did not know how to correctly perform the simplest mathematical operations continued to experience the same problems at school. Since the program of further education in mathematics involves changes in the direction of complexity, it becomes obvious that a student who does not have the skills to perform the simplest actions of mathematics, in this case, addition and subtraction, will continue to lag behind his classmates who do not have such problems. And this can significantly affect the self-esteem of underachieving students and, as a result, reduce their interest in schoolwork, which in turn will lead to general underachievement. It must be admitted that in the presence of a huge number of studies aimed at studying teaching methods in the primary grades of a secondary general education school, there are not so many of them that are devoted specifically to the problems of teaching mathematics in this period. In addition, there are no serious assessments of the effectiveness of pedagogical technologies.[2] There are even fewer who consider how teaching methods can affect underperforming students. Why is the study of problems related to the teaching of mathematics so important? Because it was found that a student who did poorly in this subject, first in primary school and then in high school, continued to show disappointing results in subsequent stages of education. As a result, in the future, such a student was forced to choose as a profession those types of activities that do not require an in-depth knowledge of mathematics. And this means that initially such a student acted as an outsider who has to be content with low pay for such work. As a result, in the future they are sure to fall into a group that can quickly lose their jobs due to

their low qualifications. All this shows how important knowledge of mathematics is for every person in our time. [4]

But, it must be admitted, these methods either do not have any positive effect on the success of students, or they help only those guys who are already well versed in mathematics, leaving weaker classmates far behind. It is known that in the teaching of mathematics, methods are used that can be divided into four groups: 1) Managerial Method: This is our more traditional method of teaching, in which teachers first showed how to solve problems and then asked students to try on their own to solve a similar problem. This technology is used everywhere. Has its advantages and disadvantages. The positive side of this method is that the student sees a visual demonstration of the solution of a mathematical problem and the application in practice of the rules of the lesson topic studied in this topic. Using the problem solved by the teacher as an example, he learns to easily solve such problems. The negative point of this technology can be called the fact that for the most part, unsuccessful students in such cases remain, as it were, in the shadow of the leaders. All their actions come down to writing off tasks solved by others. It is clear that at the same time such a student will not learn the material taught in the lesson. Why is this method called managerial? Because in it the teacher manages the entire process of the lesson, taking on the main points. 2) Student-centered model: This method involves the work of students divided into groups. It allows children working in a group to create their own mathematical hypotheses and apply them to real life. 3) Manipulative-calculative method. Involves children working with physical objects to solve math problems or used calculators. 4) The "movement music" method. It includes methods in which students move themselves and use musical accompaniment.[3] All these methods are aimed at improving the perception of the topics of the mathematics program. When teaching this discipline in the primary grades, the managerial method and the "music movement" technology are more effective. The first named method is preferable because in the primary grades the child still experiences an urgent need for a mentor who can guide him on the right path to solving the problem, encouraging his striving for diligence. At this age, children are vulnerable to criticism from the outside, tend to follow all the instructions of the teacher and often blindly obey his instructions. But with the systematic use of this method, the student may get bored: a monotonous explanation and subsequent independent solution of the problem will be repeated every day. The child has a decrease in attention to the material being studied, he ceases to delve into the essence of the issue. [5] For this reason, an experienced teacher should be able to feel such a moment. In such cases, the "movement music" method comes to the rescue. This technology is remarkable precisely for the presence in it of an element of movement accompanied by music. Pupils who are still under the influence of the orders adopted in preschool institutions study in the primary grades. And they involve a lot of movement.

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